

Improving Massive Access to IoT Gateways

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Abstract

IoT networks handle incoming packets from large numbers of IoT Devices (IoTDs) to IoT Gateways. This can lead to the IoT Massive Access Problem that causes buffer overflow, large end-to-end delays and missed deadlines. This paper analyzes a novel traffic shaping method named the Quasi-Deterministic Traffic Policy (QDTP) that mitigates this problem by shaping the incoming traffic without increasing the end-to-end delay or dropping packets. Using queueing theoretic techniques and extensive data driven simulations with real IoT datasets, the value of QDTP is shown as a means to considerably reduce congestion at the Gateway, and significantly improve the IoT network's overall performance.

Key words: Internet of Things (IoT); Traffic Shaping at IoT Devices; IoT Gateway Congestion; Massive Access Problem; Queueing Theory; Quasi Deterministic Transmission Policy (QDTP)

1. Introduction

Sensors for health applications, smart meters, the monitoring of remote areas which are of difficult access, and the monitoring of large civil engineering structures [40, 50, 21] are a few of the numerous applications covered by the Internet of Things (IoT). These networks of connected devices of different types also address the needs of autonomous systems, smart cities and smart vehicles [10, 5].

However increased IoT connectivity also increases the amount of traffic that such networks must carry, and can thus result in serious congestion known as the Massive Access Problem (MAP) of the IoT where IoT Gateways (IoTG) can suffer high levels of congestion, resulting in packet losses, long end-to-end delays and missed deadlines [51, 20].

It is difficult to coordinate, synchronize or jointly schedule large numbers of simple interconnected IoT devices (IoTD), which in addition may have timing data (such as internal clocks) with random differences in value [17, 6, 11]. Thus rather than dealing

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with the sources of IoT traffic themselves, MAP was addressed in early research [14], through adaptive routing to reduce congestion by using multiple paths and gateways, and by using information theory to reduce the amount of data that is forwarded [32, 16]. Proactive approaches [9, 35, 36, 39], including adaptive traffic storage and offloading to less congested gateways [8], were also suggested.

Many other papers [26, 51, 27, 2, 42, 24, 20, 25, 41, 3], suppose that IoT traffic is random, and propose to mitigate MAP via a variety of techniques such as Access Class Barring (ACB), [24, 28, 47, 48], Cognitive Machine-to-Machine (M2M) communications, [1], game theory [33], device clustering [34], adaptation of packet rates, [43], Spread-spectrum Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) [42], Interference Cancellation (SIC), [51], CSMA/CA and slotted-ALOHA [41], and collision awareness [3].

On the other hand it was empirically shown that IoT traffic at the MAC-layer may be predicted with Machine Learning (ML) to help identify distinct IoT traffic classes [30]. Thus in [31], the predictability of IoT traffic was used to address the MAP with a Joint Forecasting-Scheduling system (JFS) that allocates time slots of a single frequency channel for IoT devices based on forecasting the instants at which traffic is generated.

In [37], a multi-scale algorithm to improve the performance of JFS was presented, while in [38] an extension of JFS for multi-frequency channels was proposed. This research has shown that predictive networks, in particular JFS, are a promising solution to the MAP, and that lightweight scheduling heuristics are useful because optimal algorithms typically have large computational requirements.

Recent work [29], shows that for any given number of IoTDTs, the statistics of the actual instants at which IoT packets are sent can significantly impact the number of packets which are received before the packets' deadlines expire. Also, "smoothing" the traffic by distributing individual packet transmission times in some uniform manner can substantially improve performance and mitigate the MAP. Conventional queueing analysis can be used to select these randomization instants, and predict which packets will not meet their deadlines so as to drop them before transmission and avoid congestion for the remaining traffic.

Recent work presented at the Mascots'21 conference [13], seeks the best way to forward packets at the sources of traffic which are the IoTDTs to minimize delay at the IoTG, and suggests a novel traffic shaping technique called the Quasi-Deterministic Traffic Policy (QDTP).

Traffic shaping is widely used in networks [22], to reduce latency, and optimize the bandwidth available for certain packets by delaying others. Typically applied at the source or edge, it is defined by the ITU [23], as a scheme which "*alters the traffic characteristics of a stream of cells ... to achieve a desired modification of those traffic characteristics, in order to achieve better network efficiency whilst meeting the QoS objectives or to ensure conformance ... with the consequence of increasing the mean cell transfer delay.*" Though traffic shaping is accomplished by delaying packets, it is sometimes confused with "traffic policing" which includes preventive packet dropping [7], through traffic shaping results in more delay for some packets and thus can cause packet loss in finite buffers. Both techniques have been discussed for ATM by [19, 45], IP [4], and Sensor Networks where traffic shaping with adaptive routing was also studied [15].

The key idea behind QDTP is to delay packets at the IoTD at most D (fixed) time units, to obtain more regularly timed arrivals at the IoTG. Experiments with real IoT data [49], and diffusion approximations reported in [13], show the effectiveness of QDTP to alleviate the MAP and improve QoS. A subsequent paper [18], shows with theoretical sample path analysis that QDTP does **not increase the overall end-to-end delay of packets** as compared to an ordinary FIFO policy, including the traffic shaping delay and the delay at the IoTG.

This paper extends the results of [13, 18] using queueing theory and validates them with trace driven simulations using real data. In particular, the present work shows that QDTP substantially reduces the average queueing delay at the IoTG with respect to a simple end-to-end First-In-First-Out (FIFO) policy, and also results in low packet backlog at each IoTD.

2. An Example of IoT Data

To illustrate some of the statistics obtained from real IoT data available from the Open Source Repository [49], in Figure 1 we show the distribution of the amount of data in bits from data bursts emanating from the IoT devices in the data set. We observe that the average number of bits per burst is 6.8167 and the Squared Coefficient of Variation (SCV) i.e. the variance divided by the square of the mean, of the number of bits per burst is 1.9506. There are only 2000 bursts with more than 50 bits per burst. For those bursts with less than 50 bits, the average number of bits per burst is 6.778 and the SCV of the number of bits per burst is 1.7633.

Figure 1: The histogram of the number of bits transmitted per burst, by the set of IoT devices, obtained from the Open Source Data Set [49].

In Figure 2, we have used the same data set, but assumed that each burst from an IoT device is sent in the form of an IP packet with a 21-byte header, and that the bits belonging to the burst are stored in bytes inside each packet, so that we exhibit the histogram of the length of the packets in bytes.

In this data set, only 2000 packets are longer than 30 bytes. We note that the overall average packet length is 22.4744 bytes with a SCV of 0.0031. If we only consider just

Figure 2: The histogram of the number of bytes transmitted per packet by the set of IoT devices, obtained from the Open Source Data Set [49], where we assume that the bursts are forwarded in the form of IP packets.

those packets whose length is less than 30 bytes, the statistics are hardly different, since the average packet length is 22.4695 bytes with a SCV of 0.0028 and the amount of payload data transmitted per burst is on average around 12 bits.

In the data driven simulations presented in Section 4, we normalize the average service time at the IoTG so that the average packet length of 22.4744 bytes is transmitted in 40 msec, and the maximum “unsaturated” traffic rate $\lambda = 1$ corresponds to 25 packets/sec.

In Figure 3 we also show the data we have extracted regarding the corresponding packet arrival rates from the same dataset, for 3000, 5000, 7000, 9000 IoTDs (devices). We notice an initial transient behaviour when many devices transmit as they get started, and then a more time-independent behaviour with random fluctuations for all of the datasets with different numbers of IoTDs, with an average arrival rate in packets/second which obviously depend on the number of IoTDs.

3. QDTP versus FIFO Queueing

In this section we define and review QDTP and compare its performance with the FIFO policy which does not use traffic shaping.

Consider a sequence of packets (or customers C_n , $n \geq 0$) that are created at IoT devices (IoTds), described by a sequence of variables:

$$\{(a_n, S_n) : n \geq 1\}, \quad (1)$$

which are the intrinsic characteristics of each successive packet, where:

- The $0 = a_0 \leq a_1 \leq a_2, \dots$ are the packet creation instants at the collection of IoTds; the time intervals between the creation of successive packets $A_{n+1} = a_{n+1} - a_n$, $n \geq 0$. Note that the packets are created at any of the IoTds, so that each a_n is the time stamp of the n -th packet, and successive packets may or may not originate at the same IoTD.

Figure 3: Packet arrival rates from different numbers M of IoT devices (IoTds), ranging from 3000 (upper box) up to 9000 devices (the lowest box), extracted from the TÜBITAK data set [49], averaged on successive 1-second time intervals of, and shown for the period of 700 seconds.

- In order to shape the traffic, the **IoTd delays the transmission of a packet using QDTP** as follows; the packet whose time-stamp is a_n is sent from the IoTd to

the IoTG at time t_n defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} t_0 &= a_0, \\ t_{n+1} &= a_{n+1} \text{ if } a_{n+1} \geq t_n + D_n \\ t_{n+1} &= t_n + D_n, \text{ otherwise, } \forall n \geq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $D_n \geq 0$. Note that the concept of QDTP described in [13] is extended to allow successive QDTP delays to vary with n as in [18].

- After the traffic shaping delay at the IoTD that we denote by $W_n^{QDTP} = t_n - a_n$, the n -th packet is transmitted by the IoTD and arrives at the IoTG. Thus we are assuming that transmission times from IoTDs to the IoTG, which typically use high-speed wireless connections, are negligible as compared to the other times of interest, such as the D_n or the service (or processing and forwarding) times at the IoTG denoted by S_n , where packets arrive at $\{t_n, n \geq 0\}$ and are served in First-In-First-Out (FIFO) order.

Figure 4 shows the timing at the IoTG when packets are sent out from the IoTDs as soon as the packets are created, i.e. at their time-stamp, so that there is **no QDTP traffic shaping** or $D = 0$, and the whole system is simply a FIFO queue. On the other hand, Figure 5 describes the system that operates with QDTP.

The well-known Lindley's Equation [46, 44], provides a recursive formula for computing the pure waiting time (before processing) of the successive packets when IoTDs forward each packet to the IoTG as soon as it assembled at the source, i.e. at time a_n without QDTP, and then the IoTG processes packets in FIFO order:

$$W_{n+1}^{FIFO} = [W_n^{FIFO} + S_n - A_{n+1}]^+, \quad W_1^{FIFO} = 0, \quad n \geq 1. \quad (3)$$

where for a real number X , we denote $[X]^+ = X$ if $X > 0$, and $[X]^+ = 0$ if $X \leq 0$. Thus if the IoTG acts as a FIFO processor and forwarder, the packet that arrives to it at time a_n will have been processed and forwarded out of the IoTG, towards (for instance) a local edge server or a Cloud server, at time $d_n = a_n + W_n^{FIFO} + S_n$.

Also, for the FIFO system without the QDTP policy the ordinary end-to-end response time, which includes the waiting time and the service time, is :

$$R_n^{FIFO} = W_n^{FIFO} + S_n. \quad (4)$$

On the other hand, QDTP (2) is defined via the sequence of forwarding or release times t_n so that the packet arriving at a_n at the IoTD, is only released at some time t_n into the FIFO queue at the IoTG for servicing, with $t_0 = a_0 = 0$, and:

$$t_{n+1} = \max\{t_n + D_n, a_{n+1}\}, \quad n \geq 0, \quad (5)$$

where $D_n \geq 0$. Obviously, when $D_n = 0, \forall n \geq 0$, we have the ordinary undelayed FIFO service. The following properties of QDTP follow from well known queueing theoretic techniques and are stated without proof.

Figure 4: Schematic representation of an IoT Gateway operating as a FIFO forwarding node without traffic shaping at the IoT devices. The packet that arrives at instant a_n waits in the buffer until it arrives at the head of the queue. It then receives service of duration S_n and leaves the server at time d_n . Its waiting time is W_n^{FIFO} , so that the departure instant is $d_n = a_n + W_n^{FIFO} + S_n$.

Theorem 1 The waiting times of packets at the IoT Ds using QDTP satisfy a relation that is identical to Lindley's equation with service times D_n , $n \geq 0$:

$$W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTD} = [W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} + D_n - A_{n+1}]^+, \quad n \geq 0. \quad (6)$$

and when the inter-arrival times $\{A_n, n \geq 1\}$ are independent and identically distributed random variables with $E[A_{n+1}] > D_n$, the well known "stability result" follows:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} = W^{QDTP-IoTD} \text{ in distribution,} \quad (7)$$

where $\text{Prob}[W < \infty] = 1$,

where (7) follows from Lindley's equation specialized to the GI/GI/1 queue with general independent interarrival times and deterministic service [44] given in (6).

Theorem 2 [18] If $D_n \leq S_n$ for all $n \geq 1$, it follows that $W_n^{QDTP-IoTGD} + W_n^{IoTG-QDTP} \leq W_n^{FIFO}$, so that QDTP does not increase the total response time for each customer or packet. The proof is provided in the Appendix.

3.1. Evaluating the QDTP Improvement for a Poisson Arrival Process

We know from *Theorem 1*, and specifically from (8) that for each successive packet, the end-to-end response time (from entering the IoT D to exiting from the IoTG) R_n^{QDTP} ,

Figure 5: Schematic representation of IoTDs operating with the Quasi-Deterministic-Transmission-Policy. Successive packets at the IoTDs are delayed by at most a fixed D amount of time before they are forwarded to the IoTG. The packet that arrives at instant a_n at its IoTD, waits until instant $t_n = a_n + W_n^{QDTP}$ and then is forwarded to the IoTG. The gateway receives the n -th packet and services it in FIFO order with a service time of duration S_n and leaves the server at time $\delta_n = a_n + W_n^{QDTP} + W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} + S_n$, where $W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTG} = [W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} + S_n - (t_{n+1} - t_n)]^+$ is Lindley's equation for the IoTG when QDTP is being used.

cannot exceed the corresponding end-to-end-delay when we use the simple FIFO algorithm R_n^{FIFO} : using :

$$\begin{aligned} R_n^{QDTP} &= W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} + W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} + S_n \\ &\leq R_n^{FIFO} = W_n^{FIFO} + S_n, \quad n \geq 1, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

which is a sample path property that does not make any restrictive assumptions about the arrival process and service times, nor about D (which does not need to be deterministic) and the interarrival or service times. As a consequence we have:

$$\begin{aligned} &W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} \\ &\leq R_n^{FIFO} - W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} - S_n = W_n^{FIFO} - W_n^{QDTP-IoTD}, \quad n \geq 1. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Restricting oneself to the case where the interarrival times of successive packets to the IoTD are independent and identically distributed, and so are the successive service times at the IoTG, we know that [44], if $D < E[A_n]$ and $E[S_n] < E[A_n]$, then following [18]:

$$\begin{aligned} &W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} \rightarrow W_n^{QDTP-IoTD}, \quad W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} \rightarrow W_n^{QDTP-IoTG}, \\ &R_n^{FIFO} \rightarrow R_n^{FIFO}, \quad \text{in distribution,} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

and

$$\text{Prob}[W^{QDTP-IoTG} < \infty] = 1, \text{ Prob}[R^{FIFO} < \infty] = 1, \quad (11)$$

In particular, if the arrival process is Poisson of rate λ and the service times $\{S_n, n \geq 1\}$ are independent and identically distributed random variables with average value $E[S] < \lambda^{-1}$ and SCV C_S^2 , and the QDTP delays $\{D_n, n \geq 1\}$ are also random variables with $D_n \leq S_n$, expected values $E[D_n] < \lambda^{-1}$ and SQV C_D^2 , then by (9) and (10) we have:

$$\text{Prob}[W^{QDTP-IoTG} \leq W^{FIFO}] = 1, \quad (12)$$

and the Pollaczek-Khintchine formula [12], for the M/G/1 queue yields:

$$E[W^{QDTP-IoTG}] \leq \frac{\rho(1 + C_S^2)}{2(\frac{1}{E[S]} - \lambda)} - \frac{\rho_D(1 + C_D^2)}{2(\frac{1}{E[D]} - \lambda)}, \quad (13)$$

where $\rho = \lambda E[S]$ and $\rho_D = \lambda E[D]$, leading to the following interesting result.

Result 2 If the arrivals are Poisson, the $S_n, n \geq 1$ and $D_n, n \geq 1$ are independent and identically distributed and both sequences have identical distributions, then:

$$E[W^{QDTP-IoTG}] = 0. \quad (14)$$

On the other hand, if $D = E[S]$ is constant and hence $C_D^2 = 0$, we have:

$$E[W^{QDTP-IoTG}] \leq \frac{\rho C_S^2}{2(\frac{1}{E[S]} - \lambda)}. \quad (15)$$

In addition, assuming that M IoTDs are the sources of the packets, and that traffic is equally provided by each source, we see that the packet backlog at each IoTD source can be computed via Little's Formula [44], to obtain:

$$N^{QDTP-IoTD} = \frac{\lambda}{M} \cdot E[W^{QDTP-IoTD}] = \frac{\rho_D(1 + C_D^2)}{2M(1 - \rho_D)}, \quad (16)$$

which tends to zero as $M \rightarrow \infty$.

These results tell us that:

2.1 if we use QDTP and each of the values D for successive packets are **not constant**, but instead are independent and identically distributed (iid) random variables, represented by the common random variable $D \leq S_n$ which tracks the first two moments of the statistics of the packet processing times S_n (which are also *iid*) at the IoTG so that $E[D] = E[S]$ and $E[D^2] = E[S^2]$, assuming that arrivals are Poisson to the IoTDs, then the waiting time at the IoTG is in effect zero and **no queue forms at the IoTG**.

2.2 If on the other hand, D is a constant with $D = E[S]$, then the average waiting time at the IoTG is given by (15).

2.3 In all cases, for any given incoming packet traffic rate λ , the backlog becomes smaller when the number M of IoTD sources increases.

In the next section one can see that these claims with Poisson arrivals are actually supported with similar results using trace driven simulations with the [49] dataset.

4. Evaluations with the TÜBITAK Dataset

In this section we provide trace-driven simulation results of queues at the gateway and at the IoTDs, both for the FIFO policy without traffic shaping, and with the QDTP traffic shaping policy. The results are summarized in Figures 6 and 7 for a service time per packet at the IoTG which is set to 40 milliseconds. The QDTP fixed delay is set to the same value $D = 40$ msec.

Figure 6 focuses on the average queue lengths over each successive one second interval at the IoTG, and compares FIFO versus QDTP, covering 700 successive seconds of operation based on the TÜBITAK dataset [49]. The number of IoTDs on the distinct curves are $M = 3000$ for the one at the top, then downwards with $M = 5000$, $M = 7000$ and $M = 9000$ IoTDs. These measurements that are summarized on each of the curves, show the substantial improvement obtained with QDTP (blue) as compared to the ordinary FIFO policy at the IoTG (red). The improvements are most striking when congestion is highest at $M = 9000$.

On the other hand, Figure 7 examines the possible buildup of packet queues at each of the IoT devices, under the assumption that they all provide an equal fraction of the packets. Indeed, FIFO will not result in any queue build-up at the IoTDs, while QDTP which delays the packet transmission will necessarily result in some form of queue build-up at the devices. In the four curves shown for $M = 3000, 5000, 7000, 9000$ that use **the same service time $E[S] = 40$ msec at the IoTG**, we see that on average the IoTDs have queues with average length well under one packet, which indicates that QDTP does not build up significant backlog at the IoT devices.

Another evaluation using the dataset in [49] uses trace driven simulations with real arrival data as shown in Figure 8, where for each value of M the average service time at the IoTG is set to a value “just under” saturation, namely $E[S] = 40$ msec. for $M = 3000$ (as in Figure 7), but $E[S] = 20$ msec for $M = 5000$, $E[S] = 15$ msec for $M = 7000$ and $M = 12$ msec for $M = 9000$. The results of Figure 8 show once again the significant improvement in IoTG queue length achieved by using QDTP in comparison to FIFO.

5. Conclusion

A major challenge for IoT networks using a large number of IoT devices, is the congestion that occurs at IoT gateways. This can result in packet loss, and hence also lost information or data, or missed deadlines that can cause inconsistencies for real-time applications such as Industrie 4.0.

To mitigate this effect, several authors have suggested predictive network scheduling based on sophisticated algorithms that analyse the data streams using computationally costly Machine Learning methods. Techniques that use such predictions to selectively drop traffic have also been suggested.

This paper completes and extends earlier work [13], and investigates a traffic shaping approach called QDTP to reduce the undesirable effects of the MAP. QDTP does not drop any traffic but simply delays packets in a specific manner at the IoTDs, so that packets arriving at the IoTG result in far shorter packet queues.

Figure 6: Queue lengths at the gateway (IoTG) with FIFO versus QDTP transmission policies, plotted versus time up to 700 seconds. The service time per packet at the IoTG is set to 40 milliseconds. For QDTP we also set $D = 40$ msec. Packet arrival times obtained for $M = 3000$ up to $M = 9000$ IoTDs, are extracted from the TÜBITAK data set [49]. The measurements that are reported show the substantial improvement obtained with QDTP (blue) as compared to the ordinary FIFO policy at the gateway (red).

We have analyzed QDTP with conventional queueing theoretic sample path methods, without any constraining assumptions on the arrival process and service times, showing that QDTP does not increase the overall packet end-to-end delay, as compared to a simple FIFO policy that forwards packets to the gateway from the IoTDs as soon as the packets are generated. The sample path analysis has also provided inequalities regarding the delay of packets at the gateway (IoTG) itself. We also analyzed QDTP under the assumption of independent and identically distributed interarrival and service times to derive inequalities regarding the end-to-end and IoTG packet delays in steady-state. Then, Poisson packet generation instants have been assumed, to obtain simple numerical expressions for the average effective QDTP delay incurred by packets,

Figure 7: Average queue lengths, measured within each successive one second time slot, at the IoTDs with FIFO (red) versus QDTP (blue) transmission policies, plotted versus time running up to 700 seconds. These simulations are conducted with packet arrival times extracted for $M = 3000$ up to $M = 9000$ IoTDs from the TÜBITAK dataset [49], assuming that each IoTd provides an equal share of the flow. We see that in all cases the IoTd queue lengths with QDTP remain negligibly small, on average well under one packet. Note that if we do not use QDTP, and just forward packets directly to the IoTG in FIFO order, no queue will form at the devices.

and an upper bound for the IoTG with QDTP.

Then, real data [49] from many thousand IoT devices has offered the opportunity to study the packet queue buildup both with FIFO and QDTP, showing the very significant queue length reduction obtained by using QDTP at the gateway. In addition, data driven simulations have allowed us to show that QDTP results in short queue lengths at each individual device (IoTd), when all the IoTds generate an equal fraction of the packet traffic.

Future research will combine QDTP with priority policies to seek further improvements in smart management of IoT networks to alleviate the MAP. Further research is

Figure 8: Average queue lengths, measured within each successive one second time slot, at the IoTDs with FIFO (red) versus QDTP (blue) transmission policies, plotted versus time running up to 700 seconds conducted with real arrival instants from the [49] dataset, where for each value of M the average service time at the IoTG is set to a value that insures that saturation does not occur, namely $E[S] = 40\text{ ms}$ for $M = 3000$ (as in Figure 7), as well as $E[S] = 20\text{ ms}$ for $M = 5000$, $E[S] = 15\text{ ms}$ for $M = 7000$ and $M = 12\text{ ms}$ for $M = 9000$. The results the significant reduction in IoTG queue length obtained via by QDTP in comparison to FIFO.

also needed to investigate smart adaptive policies that tune the traffic shaping delays to ongoing traffic loads and delays in IoT networks, and to the conditions in individual IoT devices and gateways.

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Appendix: Proof of Theorem 2

The proof follows closely the approach presented in [18], and is by induction:

- The **basis** of the induction is $0 = W_0^{QDTP-IoTD} + W_0^{QDTP-IoTG} = 0 \leq W^{FIFO} = 0$.
- The **step** of the induction is to assume that the statement is true for some $n > 0$:

$$W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} + W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} \leq W_n^{FIFO}, \text{ for some } n \geq 1, \quad (17)$$

and prove that it is true for $n + 1$,
i.e. we must prove that:

$$W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTD} + W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTG} \leq W_{n+1}^{FIFO}. \quad (18)$$

To prove (18) we use $W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} \leq W_n^{FIFO} - W_n$ and have:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{n+1}^{FIFO} &= [W_n^{FIFO} + S_n - A_{n+1}]^+, \text{ and} \\ W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTD} + W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTG} &\leq [W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} D_n - A_{n+1}]^+ \\ &\quad + [W_n^{FIFO} - W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} S_n - A_{n+1} - W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTD} + W_n]^+, \\ &\leq [W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} D_n - A_{n+1}]^+ \\ &\quad + [W_n^{FIFO} + S_n - A_{n+1} - W_{n+1}]^+. \end{aligned}$$

There are two cases to consider, A) and B):

- A) If $W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} D_n - A_{n+1} \leq 0$, which implies that $W_{n+1} = 0$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTD} + W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTG} &= [W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} + S_n - A_{n+1} + W_n]^+ \\ &= [W_n^{FIFO} + S_n - A_{n+1}]^+ = W_{n+1}^{FIFO}, \end{aligned}$$

so that using the induction step $W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} \leq W_n^{FIFO}$, we have proved for case A) that $W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTD} + W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTG} \leq W_{n+1}^{FIFO}$.

- B) On the other hand if $W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} D_n - A_{n+1} > 0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTD} + W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTG} &= W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} D_n - A_{n+1} \\ &\quad + [W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} + S_n - A_{n+1} - W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTD} + W_n]^+, \\ &= W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} D_n - A_{n+1} + [W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} + S_n - D_n]^+. \end{aligned}$$

Since $W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} \geq 0$ and $S_n \geq D_n$ we know that:

$$W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} + S_n - D_n > 0,$$

and as a consequence:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTD} + W_{n+1}^{QDTP-IoTG} &= \\ &= W_n^{QDTP-IoTD} D_n - A_{n+1} + W_n^{QDTP-IoTG} + S_n - D_n, \\ &= W_n^{FIFO} + S_n - A_{n+1} \\ &\leq W_{n+1}^{FIFO} = [W_n^{FIFO} + S_n - A_{n+1}]^+. \end{aligned}$$

In addition, since the delay $W_n^{QDTP-IoTD}$ at the IoTD is non-negative, and the total delay at the IoTD plus at the IoTG $W_n^{QDTP-IoTG}$ is no greater than the delay of an ordinary FIFO gateway W_n^{FIFO} , the delay and buffer queue length at the IoTG will be reduced. **This completes the proof of Theorem 2.**

References

- [1] Adnan Aijaz and A Hamid Aghvami. 2015. Cognitive machine-to-machine communications for Internet-of-Things: A protocol stack perspective. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 2, 2 (2015), 103–112.
- [2] Adnan Aijaz, Shuyu Ping, Mohammad Reza Akhavan, and Abdol-Hamid Aghvami. 2014. CRB-MAC: A receiver-based MAC protocol for cognitive radio equipped smart grid sensor networks. *IEEE Sensors Journal* 14, 12 (2014), 4325–4333.
- [3] Zahra Alavikia and Abdorasoul Ghasemi. 2018. Collision-aware resource access scheme for LTE-based machine-to-machine communications. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology* 67, 5 (2018), 4683–4688.
- [4] D. O. Awduche. 1999. MPLS and Traffic Engineering in IP Networks. *IEEE Comm. Mag.* 37, 12 (December 1999), 42–47.
- [5] Oladayo Bello and Sherali Zeadally. 2019. Toward efficient smartification of the Internet of Things (IoT) services. *Future Generation Computer Systems* 92 (2019), 663–673.
- [6] A. Chesnais, Erol Gelenbe, and Isi Mitrani. 1983. On the Modeling of Parallel Access to Shared Data. *Commun. ACM* 26, 3 (1983), 196–202.
- [7] CISCO. 2005. Comparing Traffic Policing and Traffic Shaping for Bandwidth Limiting. *Cisco Tech Notes, Document ID: 19645* (August 2005).
- [8] Jun Du, Erol Gelenbe, Chunxiao Jiang, Haijun Zhang, and Yong Ren. 2017. Contract design for traffic offloading and resource allocation in heterogeneous ultra-dense networks. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* 35, 11 (2017), 2457–2467.
- [9] Yalda Edalat, Jong-Suk Ahn, and Katia Obraczka. 2016. Smart experts for network state estimation. *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management* 13, 3 (2016), 622–635.
- [10] Giancarlo Fortino, Wilma Russo, Claudio Savaglio, Mirko Viroli, and MengChu Zhou. 2017. Modeling Opportunistic IoT Services in Open IoT Ecosystems.. In *WOA*. 90–95.
- [11] Erol Gelenbe and Georges Hébrail. 1986. A Probability Model of Uncertainty in Data Bases. In *ICDE*. IEEE Computer Society, 328–333.

- [12] Erol Gelenbe and Israel Mitrani. 2010. *Analysis and Synthesis of Computer Systems, 2nd Edition*. World Scientific, Imperial College Press. 324 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1142/p643>
- [13] Erol Gelenbe, Mert Nakip, Dariusz Marek, and Tadeusz Czachórski. 2021. Diffusion Analysis Improves Scalability of IoT Networks to Mitigate the Massive Access Problem. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Modelling, Analysis and Simulation of Computer and Telecommunication Systems (MAS-COTS'21)*. IEEE Computer Society, 1–8.
- [14] Erol Gelenbe and Edith C.-H. Ngai. 2008. Adaptive qos routing for significant events in wireless sensor networks. In *2008 5th IEEE International Conference on Mobile Ad Hoc and Sensor Systems*. IEEE, 410–415.
- [15] Erol Gelenbe and Edith C.-H. Ngai. 2010. Adaptive random re-routing for differentiated QoS in sensor networks. *Comput. J.* 53, 7 (2010), 1052–1061.
- [16] Erol Gelenbe, Edith C. H. Ngai, and Poonam Yadav. 2010. Routing of high-priority packets in wireless sensor networks. In *IEEE Second International Conference on Computer and Network Technology, IEEE*.
- [17] Erol Gelenbe and Ken Sevcik. 1979. Analysis of update synchronization for multiple copy data bases. *IEEE Trans. Comput.* 10 (1979), 737–747.
- [18] Erol Gelenbe and Karl Sigman. 2022. IoT Traffic Shaping and the Massive Access Problem. In *Proceedings IEEE International Communications Conference 2022*. IEEEExplore, 2290–2295.
- [19] E. Gelenbe, V. Srinivasan, S. Seshadri, and N. Gautam. 2001. Optimal Policies for ATM Cell Scheduling and Rejection. *Telecommunication Systems* 18 (2001), 331–358. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1016782028027>
- [20] Fayeze Ghavimi and Hsiao-Hwa Chen. 2015. M2M communications in 3GPP LTE/LTE-A networks: Architectures, service requirements, challenges, and applications. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials* 17, 2 (2015), 525–549.
- [21] Md. Ershadul Haque, Md. Asikuzzaman, Imran Ullah Khan, In-Ho Ra, Md. Sanwar Hossain, and Syed Bilal Hussain Shah. 2020. Comparative Study of IoT-Based Topology Maintenance Protocol in a Wireless Sensor Network for Structural Health Monitoring. *Remote. Sens.* 12, 15 (2020), 2358. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12152358>
- [22] IETF. 1988. An Architecture for Differentiated Services. *ETF RFC 2475* (December 1988).
- [23] ITU. 2004. Traffic control and congestion control in B-ISDN. *ITU-T Recommendation I.371* (March 2004).
- [24] Hu Jin, Waqas Tariq Toor, Bang Chul Jung, and Jun-Bae Seo. 2017. Recursive pseudo-Bayesian access class barring for M2M communications in LTE systems. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology* 66, 9 (2017), 8595–8599.

- [25] Liang Liang, Lu Xu, Bin Cao, and Yunjian Jia. 2018. A Cluster-Based Congestion-Mitigating Access Scheme for Massive M2M Communications in Internet of Things. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 5, 3 (2018), 2200–2211.
- [26] Shao-Yu Lien, Tzu-Huan Liau, Ching-Yueh Kao, and Kwang-Cheng Chen. 2012. Cooperative access class barring for machine-to-machine communications. *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications* 11, 1 (2012), 27–32.
- [27] Tzu-Ming Lin, Chia-Han Lee, Jen-Po Cheng, and Wen-Tsuen Chen. 2014. PRADA: Prioritized random access with dynamic access barring for MTC in 3GPP LTE-A networks. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology* 63, 5 (2014), 2467–2472.
- [28] Jianlong Liu, Lijun Song, et al. 2017. A novel congestion reduction scheme for massive machine-to-machine communication. *IEEE Access* 5 (2017), 18765–18777.
- [29] Mert Nakip and Erol Gelenbe. 2021. Randomization of Data Generation Times Improves Performance of Predictive IoT Networks. In *2021 IEEE World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT)* (New Orleans, Louisiana). IEEEExplore, 1–6. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4696170>
- [30] Mert Nakip, Baran Can Gül, Volkan Rodoplu, and Cüneyt Güzeliş. 2019. Comparative study of forecasting schemes for IoT device traffic in machine-to-machine communication. In *Proceedings of the 2019 4th International Conference on Cloud Computing and Internet of Things*. 102–109.
- [31] Mert Nakip, Volkan Rodoplu, Cüneyt Güzeliş, and Deniz Türsel Eliyi. 2019. Joint Forecasting-Scheduling for the Internet of Things. In *2019 IEEE Global Conference on Internet of Things (GCIoT)*. IEEE, 1–7.
- [32] Edith C.-H. Ngai, Erol Gelenbe, and Gregory Humber. 2009. Information-aware traffic reduction for wireless sensor networks. In *2009 IEEE 34th Conference on Local Computer Networks*. IEEE, 451–458.
- [33] Yuan-Chi Pang, Shih-Lung Chao, Guan-Yu Lin, and Hung-Yu Wei. 2014. Network access for M2M/H2H hybrid systems: A game theoretic approach. *IEEE Communications Letters* 18, 5 (2014), 845–848.
- [34] Ieryung Park, Dohyun Kim, and Dongsoo Har. 2015. MAC achieving low latency and energy efficiency in hierarchical M2M networks with clustered nodes. *IEEE Sensors Journal* 15, 3 (2015), 1657–1661.
- [35] Vladislav Petkov and Katia Obraczka. 2012. Collision-free medium access based on traffic forecasting. In *2012 IEEE International Symposium on a World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks (WoWMoM)*. IEEE, 1–9.
- [36] Darijo Raca, Ahmed H Zahran, Cormac J Sreenan, Rakesh K Sinha, Emir Halepovic, Rittwik Jana, and Vijay Gopalakrishnan. 2020. On Leveraging Machine

- and Deep Learning for Throughput Prediction in Cellular Networks: Design, Performance, and Challenges. *IEEE Communications Magazine* 58, 3 (2020), 11–17.
- [37] Volkan Rodoplu, Mert Nakip, Deniz Türsel Eliiyi, and Cüneyt Güzelis. 2020. A Multi-Scale Algorithm for Joint Forecasting-Scheduling to Solve the Massive Access Problem of IoT. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* (2020).
- [38] Volkan Rodoplu, Mert Nakip, Roozbeh Qorbanian, and Deniz Türsel Eliiyi. 2020. Multi-Channel Joint Forecasting-Scheduling for the Internet of Things. *IEEE Access* 8 (2020), 217324–217354.
- [39] Lihua Ruan, Maluge Pubuduni Imali Dias, and Elaine Wong. 2019. Machine learning-based bandwidth prediction for low-latency H2M applications. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 6, 2 (2019), 3743–3752.
- [40] Yesin Sahraoui, Ahmed Korichi, Chaker Abdelaziz Kerrache, Muhammad Bilal, and Marica Amadeo. 2021. Remote Sensing to Control Respiratory Viral Diseases Outbreaks using Internet of Vehicles. *CoRR* abs/2103.12512 (2021). <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.12512>
- [41] Nurullah Shahin, Rashid Ali, and Young-Tak Kim. 2018. Hybrid Slotted-CSMA/CA-TDMA for Efficient Massive Registration of IoT Devices. *IEEE Access* 6 (2018), 18366–18382.
- [42] Mahyar Shirvanimoghaddam, Mischa Dohler, and Sarah J Johnson. 2017. Massive non-orthogonal multiple access for cellular IoT: Potentials and limitations. *IEEE Communications Magazine* 55, 9 (2017), 55–61.
- [43] Peng Si, Jian Yang, Shuangwu Chen, and Hongsheng Xi. 2015. Adaptive massive access management for QoS guarantees in M2M communications. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology* 64, 7 (2015), 3152–3166.
- [44] Karl Sigman. 1995. *Stationary Marked Point Processes: An Intuitive Approach*. Chapman and Hall, CRC. 200 pages.
- [45] Vijay Srinivasan, Anoop Ghanwani, and Erol Gelenbe. 1996. Block loss reduction in ATM networks. *Computer Communications* 19, 13 (1996), 1077–1091. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-3664\(96\)01135-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-3664(96)01135-8) Enabling ATM networks.
- [46] Lajos Takács. 1962. *Introduction to the Theory of Queues*. Oxford University Press.
- [47] Luis Tello-Oquendo, Israel Leyva-Mayorga, Vicent Pla, Jorge Martinez-Bauset, José-Ramón Vidal, Vicente Casares-Giner, and Luis Guijarro. 2018. Performance analysis and optimal access class barring parameter configuration in LTE-A networks with massive M2M traffic. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology* 67, 4 (2018), 3505–3520.

- [48] Luis Tello-Oquendo, Diego Pacheco-Paramo, Vicent Pla, and Jorge Martinez-Bauset. 2018. Reinforcement learning-based ACB in LTE-A networks for handling massive M2M and H2H communications. In *2018 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*. IEEE, 1–7.
- [49] TÜBITAK1001-118E277. 2021. IoT Traffic Generation Pattern Dataset. *Kaggle* (November 2021). <https://www.kaggle.com/tubitak1001118e277/iot-traffic-generation-patterns>
- [50] Abnash Zaman, Zohaib Hassan, Roman Odarchenko, Shaoib Hassan, Sheeraz Ahmed, Muhammad Bilal, Ishtiaque Ahmad, Vitalii Tiurin, and Arshia Faheem. 2020. Wireless Underground Sensor Networks: Packet Size Optimization Survey. In *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Control, Optimisation and Analytical Processing of Social Networks (COAPSN 2020), Lviv, Ukraine, May 21, 2020 (CEUR Workshop Proceedings)*, Solomiia Fedushko and Thierry Oscar Edoh (Eds.), Vol. 2616. CEUR-WS.org, 353–365. <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2616/paper30.pdf>
- [51] Andrea Zanella, Michele Zorzi, André F dos Santos, Petar Popovski, Nuno Pratas, Cedomir Stefanovic, Armin Dekorsy, Carsten Bockelmann, Bryan Busropan, and Toon AHJ Norp. 2013. M2M massive wireless access: Challenges, research issues, and ways forward. In *2013 IEEE Globecom Workshops*. IEEE, 151–156.